

OPTIMIZED SURGICAL TACTICS FOR CHRONIC COLOSTASIS

Egamov Yu.S.

Durdiev H.B.

Andijan State Medical Institute, Uzbekistan.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14214267>

The relevance of the problem. The presence of multiple etiological factors of colostasis often complicates the choice of optimal tactics [3]. At the same time, patients are carried away by self-medication without achieving the desired effect, respectively, the approaches to treatment used are not effective enough [1]. In the overwhelming majority of cases, chronic CS requires surgical treatment. However, operations are technically complex and are marred by a high frequency of unsatisfactory results, which reaches 13-30% [2;4].

The aim of the study is improving the immediate and long-term results of surgical treatment for chronic colostasis by optimizing surgical tactics.

Material and research methods. An analysis of the results of examination and treatment of 396 patients suffering from chronic constipation (colostasis) who were undergoing inpatient treatment in the proctology department of the Department of Surgery and Civil Defense of the AndGosMI Clinic and the Ellikkala District Medical Association of the Republic of Korakalpogiston was conducted.

The sample of patients upon admission was conditionally divided into two groups:

-comparison group –172 (43.4%)patients with CS in the period from 2015 to 2018, whose treatment was limited to subsequent standard patient management.

-main group-224 (56.6%)patients with CS operated on in the period 2019 to 2023, who were treated with an improved treatment and diagnostic algorithm, as well as a modified method of “immersion” invagination coloanastomosis.

To achieve the goal and objectives of the study, general clinical, laboratory, biochemical, instrumental and statistical research methods were carried out according to the protocols approved by the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan and Coracalpohistone.

Results and their discussion. Principles of therapy for patients with constipation. In the course of determining the treatment tactics for patients with chronic KS, it was recommended to keep track of the frequency of stool, the consistency and shape of feces (according to the Bristol scale), the intake of

medications, and adherence to a diet, which allows one to evaluate the effectiveness of therapy.

In the initial stage of treatment, dietary and lifestyle changes (optimizing fiber and fluid intake and encouraging regular physical activity) are carried out for all forms of CS.

Diet therapy. Low-molecular carbohydrates – oligosaccharides, fructo-oligosaccharides, galacto-oligosaccharides – also have a positive effect on chronic KS. Being essentially probiotics, this group of substances has its therapeutic effect, positively influencing the intestinal microflora. They are also not subject to hydrolysis by intestinal enzymes, are not adsorbed in the small intestine, while being a selective substrate for bifido- and lactobacilli, stimulate their growth and metabolic activity.

When prescribing drugs that increase the volume of contents in the intestine (drugs containing dietary fiber), the possibility of increasing fluid intake was assessed. The exceptions were patients with severe cardiovascular pathology, chronic liver failure, chronic renal disease, where the laxative effect of drugs that limit fluid intake is not realized.

Sports activities help activate the motor function of the TC, and additionally, the use of fiber and liquid regulates its emptying. Restoration of a regular act of defecation at a certain time is possible with the help of "irritating" candles, creating a calm, comfortable environment during defecation.

To maintain intestinal motor activity, food should be regular (4-6 times a day) with a volume of at least 2 liters per day. The menu should include coarse insoluble fiber, which enhances intestinal peristalsis. It is recommended to take fermented milk products (yogurt, kefir, acidophilus), which regulate intestinal peristalsis. Boiled vegetables and vegetable fats (sunflower or olive oil) have proven themselves.

Products containing astringents and starches should be excluded from the diet.

Drug therapy for constipation. Along with dietary measures, it is recommended to prescribe drugs that help increase the volume in the intestine, i.e. food supplements containing fermentable and non-fermentable dietary fiber. These drugs should be taken starting with 5 g of fiber per day, increasing the dose gradually at intervals of 1-2 weeks to 10-13 g per day.

Osmotic laxatives (lactulose, polyethylene glycol (PEG), lactitol) retain water in the intestine, which helps soften feces and improve their movement. This group is recommended to be used with caution in patients with renal

failure or cardiovascular pathology, due to the continued risk of electrolyte imbalance and dehydration.

Stimulant laxatives. This group includes senna, aloe, bisacodyl, sodium picosulfate, etc. These drugs are effective and are the most common among patients with CS, provided that the dose, regimen, and duration of administration are correctly selected.

When choosing the method of CS surgery for each specific patient, we approached it individually, taking into account the situation that developed during the surgery, i.e. the surgical finding. We believe that this contingent should be operated by surgeons with extensive practical experience in abdominal surgery of proctology. It is necessary to pay attention to the presence of megacolon, dolichosigma or their combination), the presence of complications and combined surgical and concomitant therapeutic pathology.

When planning operations, the patient's preparation is the same - a slag-free diet is prescribed for 1-2 days, the day before the operation, mechanical cleansing of the large intestine is performed, which has several methods. We used a combined method of cleansing the large intestine: in the evening before the patient was prescribed 2 packets of the drug Fortrans + 2 liters of water, cleansing enemas the evening before (2) and in the morning (2) before the operation.

The presence of concomitant diseases required additional treatment measures in the preoperative and postoperative periods, limited the use of infusion therapy, especially in patients with severe pathology of the cardiovascular and bronchopulmonary systems. Therefore, correct correction of this pathology is very important.

For the prevention of thromboembolic complications (TEC), clexane or fraxiparine 0.4-0.6 U were used according to indications. The treatment complex also included cardiac glycosides, cocarboxylase 150 mg per day, thiotriazoline 2.5%-4.0; B vitamins, ascorbic acid. The leading place was occupied by the fight against infection. For this purpose, broad-spectrum antibiotics and sulfonamides were used in combination with immunostimulating therapy.

Postoperative management should be considered as a continuation of a single program of treatment measures initiated during preoperative preparation and the operation itself. In the postoperative period, along with rational infusion and antibacterial therapy, as well as the introduction of painkillers, great importance was given to early stimulation of intestinal peristalsis, nutrition, early activation of the patient and prevention of thromboembolic complications.

Our main tasks of restorative correction after surgery were normalization of the motor activity of the colon due to various types of contractions of the intestinal wall, normalization of the passage of feces, restoration of the feeling of urge to defecate, and reduction of asthenovegetative disorders.

In the functional form of chronic CS, 45 patients (20.1%) were subject to conservative treatment, while 179 (79.9%) - to surgical treatment (transient form - 31 (13.8%); mixed - 148 (66.1%)). The leading indications for surgical treatment were dolichosigma detected in 80 (35.7%) patients. At the same time, left-sided dolichocolon was diagnosed in 42 (18.7%), right-sided dolichocolon in 21 (9.4%) and megacolon in 36 (16.1%) patients. Nevertheless, from other forms leading to chronic constipation, functional disorders were also diagnosed in 45 (20.1%) patients who underwent conservative treatment with a successful outcome.

In the main group (224 patients) with CS, of those operated on (179 patients), the largest number were patients with resection of the sigmoid colon - 84 (47.0%).

Other types of operations, such as subtotal colectomy were performed in 35 (19.5%), left-sided hemicolectomy in 39 (21.8%) patients, and right-sided hemicolectomy in 16 (8.9%). Colectomy was performed only in 5 (2.2%) patients.

Conclusion. Thus, surgical tactics should be based on the severity, duration of the anamnesis, gender, and concomitant therapeutic pathology, i.e. should be active diagnostic and individual when choosing the timing and methods of surgery. At the same time, surgical methods of correction of CS are accompanied by an extremely high frequency of complications and mortality.

References:

1. Achkasov S.I., Aleshin D.V. Is there still a place for surgery in the treatment of slow-transit constipation // Coloproctology. - 2018. - V.2, No. 64. - P. 7-13.
2. Sakulin K.A., Karpushin O.Yu. Treatment and diagnostic algorithm for resistant forms of colonic constipation in adults // Bulletin of modern clinical medicine. - 2021. - Vol. 14, No. 3. - P. 38-43.
3. Storr M. Chronic constipation: current management and challenges // Canadian Journal of Gastroenterology and Hepatology. - 2011. - Vol. 25. - No. Suppl B. - P. 5B-6B.
4. Yang YP, Shi J, Zhao ZY et al. Subtotal colectomy with antiperistaltic cecosigmoidal anastomosis may be another suitable option for slow transit constipation: Experiences from Chinese people // Medicine. - 2020. - V.99, No. 7. - P.1-6.